

Rome, the city of the future in the lessons of history: typological models and strategies of intervention

Introduction

The Historical City and the Contemporary City

The connotations of modernity are not always evident in recent architecture, not exclusive to it. Perhaps even today, Rome cannot define itself as a modern city, in spite of the fact that most of the buildings of the city's metropolitan area were built in the past one hundred years. Instead, it was the scale of ancient architecture, its spatial conception and language which served as starting points of many significant studies by masters of the Modern Movement. The rare quality constructions of the past century have not, in fact, been able to imprint their own language on the collective memory through the creation of spaces suitable for the public. Meanwhile, the successful and diffuse formal solutions of historical structures, though equipped with inadequate infrastructure, are evermore being forced to accommodate sometimes incompatible functions.

At the end of the XIXth century, this culture of separation already characterized the efforts to transform Rome into a modern capital. In the case of street systems, existing patterns were widened and regularized without realizing the quality of the built environment. With regards to services, buildings of the historical center were substituted by new, often overscaled, uni-functional spaces. In the case of historical monuments, their effective dimensions were ignored, thus isolating entire sectors of the city.

Still today, in the disorder of the metropolitan chaos, modern projects, projects for the reuse of

historical structures and projects for the restoration of ancient monumental complexes risk mortifying the city's identity, because they are conceived of for separate and often conflicting fields. In spite of restraints and improper transformations, any intervention must make the most of existing conditions and anticipate future needs. That is, if we don't intend on relegating the livable city to some utopia.

The objective of obtaining widespread quality urban space, such as expressed in the redundancy of the major efforts of the past or in the rationality of nineteenth century engineers and modern architects, must today base itself on the continual process of careful recognition of the urban context and the selection of uses, materials and technology which are compatible with this context.

The Ancient City and the City of the Future

It is possible, at the scale of the entire metropolitan area, to identify new parameters of intervention which, defining the project within the intrinsic qualities of its surroundings, have as their objective the requalification of recent constructions, the recovery of abandoned areas and complexes, and the protection of historical and archeological patrimony. While it started from a very sectorial point of view, this awareness has been the direction of the Soprintendenza Archeologica di Roma for the past twenty years, realizing that the ancient city provided Rome with models, structures and its very materials of construction and that it organized and gave form to a territorial settlement at a metropolitan scale on which the contemporary city still stands. The artifacts and the archeology which are present throughout the city, constitute an enormous resource, not just of symbolic imagery but as an operative part of the contemporary city. Although they are a product of antiquity, perhaps these places are the only part of the city designed to receive a tumultuous and intense number of visitors.

As a first step towards an integrated project, a piano di settore was made for the Archeological Area - at the moment within the Aurelian walls - in which various possible interventions and uses were identified, zone by zone. Throughout the city, it was then possible to envision:

- 1- the spaces to be designated for new infrastructures and new works,
- 2- the zones where new works must be preceded by an archeological survey,
- 3- the areas exclusively dedicated to conservation, thus creating completely new typologies.

In the rush to finish works in time for the year 2000 Jubilee, these prescriptions were often undervalued or ignored, resulting in belated afterthoughts and revolving controversies.

In spite of many contradictions, some projects have begun the long process towards an urban plan which is more respectful of the ancient past and more consistent with contemporary life (thus, has the archeological area of piazza Vittorio recovered its nineteenth century gardens and buildings, work is currently underway to re-establish the edges and rationalize the public services at the Baths of Caracalla, while in the area of the Coliseum and the Imperial Fora projects must await the conclusion of archeological investigations as well as the results of surveys for a proposed new subway line). In all these cases, diverse public and private entities have interacted with different competence and responsibility.

New Typological Models

In many ways, an archeological presence provides the modern city with specific guidelines for ordering itself: this occurs within the city proper, as in the case of the Imperial Fora, where the city is arranged around a vast central archeological area; in the periphery, as in the excavations at the new Auditorium; and in modern infrastructure, for example, the archeological findings that have informed the ordering of the new high speed railway.

The goal of the Soprintendenza Archeologica di Roma is to preserve the testimony of the past, and to defend it and keep it from degradation; these are choices in favor of the city. There are two well accepted methods within city planning for achieving this goal: first, the intervention of a guardian who selects projects based on the compatibility between the historic site itself and the proposed function of the ensuing renovation; and, second, the patient work of conservation that strives to restore the site to an original state, thereby opposing the natural will of each built piece to waste away. Good city planning is born from the knowledge of morphology of place, from the understanding of historic processes of construction, and from careful consideration of research and findings.

Planning such as this is indispensable to Rome, which, modernized much later than other European capitals, would like to take advantage of that tardiness and transform it (by studying and avoiding the mistakes of other twentieth century renovations of ancient sites) into a potential progress, in which it uses these recuperated spaces in a way that integrates rather than isolates them, incorporating on every level their rich historical and archeological lineage with their current cultural functions; the sites can also exist as living architectural archives for analysis of technique and material, and can become part of the heritage of a city that remains a contemporary city. One autonomous contribution of the Soprintendenza Archeologica di Roma can be seen

in the method of its intervention at the Balbo Crypt, a city block which has grown throughout the centuries among the vestiges of one of the theatres of the ancient Campus Martius. These monumental excavations and restorations, which have been under way for several years and which cover an area of almost 10,000 square meters (110,000 square feet), strive to restore activity (cultural activity and information services) to this long abandoned space.

In projects such as this, a public space characterized by its important ancient and post-ancient construction, there must be a tight connection between the excavated (dug out and on display) and restored (built up and with current function) parts of the project in order for it to be successfully reintegrated into the modern fabric of the city.

The Restoration Project of the Balbo Crypt

The theatre built in the first century BC by Lucio Cornelio Balbo on the site of the Villa Publica was composed of a hemisphere of seating, or cavea, and a wide, square portico with a structure at its center used either for cult worship or as a fountain. This form, one of the actually visible in the fragments of the Forma Urbis (the etched-stone map of Rome from the age of Septimius Severus) is still recognizable in the Renaissance structure of the city blocks and in the ancient foundations of the present buildings; the block formed by the palazzo Mattei, the palazzo Caetani, and the palazzo Paganica correspond to the cavea, and the block of the Balbo Crypt, separated from the others during the building of the via Caetani in the Renaissance, occupies entirely the ancient portico. The current space of the crypt contains the remains of two convents and some houses, all of which are of medieval origins, were renovated in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, and were partially demolished in the 1940's in the course of widening the via delle Botteghe Oscure; since then the entire area has been abandoned. Restricted from being sold by virtue of its identification as a roman monument, the site has only recently been entrusted to the Soprintendenza Archeologica di Roma, which had effected the long task of acquiring the site's scientific recognition. From the demolition of the Renaissance construction, there emerged the ruins of a sixteenth century building, monastic buildings preceding that, medieval houses before that, and, of course, of the original Roman monuments. The excavations and historic research have identified ancient bearing structures up to the upper floors of the pre-Renaissance houses and palaces; this particular city block seems, in fact, to have always been at the center of the urban life of Rome, and its surviving buildings represent and describe, in their form, materials, and same contra-

dictions, the growth and transformation of the city. The stratified excavation has revealed parts of the complex that were covered and recovered during its many different states of existence: from an abandoned state to productive, from defense to dwelling, and from its use as apartments to that of a convent. The same method of recognition applied vertically, that is, to the thick, built up layers of the walls of the building, helps to identify the borders and the connections of the origins of the building, bringing to light an extraordinary, built archive. The continuity of the Roman structures here with those of the following eras gives rise to an urban stratification of great complexity and scientific interest rare to find in a city so often renovated as Rome. However, because of the fragmentation caused by the many transformations and heavy demolitions throughout the years, along with the instability of the surviving walls, it is necessary to carry out a project of complete restoration. This restoration cannot oversimplify but must allow for a complexity of diverse yet compatible functions; it must revive adequate conditions of fully functioning contemporary services along with complete conservation of existing historical architecture. However, because no interventions on the city can be hypothesized in solely analytical terms, it is necessary to attempt to restore general discoveries to urban specifics, thereby creating a project synthesis that is capable of formulating a general strategic argument that restores form, use, and meaning to this forgotten piece of the ancient historic fabric.

The archeological monument outlined here is one of maximum value for the accumulation of civil, religious and historic meanings; it is meant to be used by the masses as sequences of administrative, civic, cultural and performance spaces, which took on new collective meanings from the presence of the medieval spaces.

The archeological area, recently brought to light in excavation, is an integral part of the Central Archeological Park that even today informs the structure of many public spaces of Rome. This could accommodate within its restored layers, both ancient and post-ancient, an information and research center relating to the conservation of the historic city, centralizing for the masses this important cultural resource.

This resource will permit the general analytical thinking and the specific project goals to be brought together in this new urban setting, adding to its complexity and multiplicity of readings. For instance, if the morphological and typological particularity of the site requires a very refined technique of survey, this refined technique (and its tools) could be exhibited as well, and with it an explanation of how it was used and what specific archeological findings it re-

corded. This could also be used in defining the form of the project of restoring the city block.

The proposal to use the Balbo Crypt as the Museo Nazionale Romano's center of medieval archeology stems from the specific nature of its site and how it correlates with what is known of ancient topography, and also with the identification of many layers of the stratified urban complex within it. This new center benefits from a privileged position in the urban archeological park and the historic paths of the ancient Campus Martius, which are home to most

of Rome's museums and cultural institutions. From this location it is possible to plan almost any desired visit: to monuments, ancient baths, sites of medieval limestone kilns, defense towers and Renaissance houses, and also to modern archives, laboratories, and rooms for study and exhibition.

Urban Stratification and Manufactured Buildings: Conservation, protection, recuperation and valorization

The scientific survey of different urban layers has enabled the identification and location of the many structures that have occupied the site of the Balbo Crypt throughout the centuries. In some of these surviving structures, identification can only be hypothesized, while in others the intact and well recognizable vertical and horizontal layers are conserved, though they may be inserted into more recent buildings. All of these edifices, resting on roman monuments and built with those monuments' recuperated materials, today are often unfit for supporting even their own weight. Therefore, during the excavation, the sequence of construction was dated, and its sequence and use recorded, and the supporting members were conserved and the added pieces removed, until the extent of the roman monuments were recognized and measured. Also recorded during this process were the historical phases of use: from ancient construction, to buildings abandoned or reused in medieval times, and on to the Renaissance and modern interventions.

This same recording method, applied vertically to the walls, and compared to source documents, has allowed for the recognition and dating of different phases of construction, of the plurality of materials, and of the techniques of construction and quality of finishing touches. This patient labor of research, under way now for more than twenty years, has enormously enriched the topographic, historic and technical knowledge the city has, but the project needs to acquire more adequate instruments to be able to continue. In this scenario, even the physical rebuilding of the various lacunae (missing parts), structures, wall fabric textures, roof systems, and architectural sections, (which would be difficult to represent at

the scale of the plan of the whole site) could be expressed by a series of explanation tags that would define to the visitor the strategy of each part of the project. Trying to explain architectural processes with words should not be interpreted as a devaluation of architectural drawing, nor should it be seen as an ambitious desire to go back to the ancient practice of making treatises. Instead it should be seen as a valid instrument of research for the synthesis of a continuous evolution of the actual state of the area and of the project. At an urban level, even the most accurate plan, façade or sectional representation of this morphological complexity with its superimposition of uses leads to the risk of being overly simplistic. At this scale, the required drawings for the definition of the recuperation plan, which are essential, are presented as inadequate for controlling the project of each building and the entire urban space. To conserve the building or one of its parts, in fact, implies assuming decisions that have to respond to architectural guidelines, while the conservation decisions derive from the specific selection of what could be restored and integrated in situ. The same singling out of which methods to adopt, although it is a fundamental part of the project, is hard to represent at the scale of the building, and even if it is represented, it would be of little operative use. Detail drawings are the only drawings that provide enough information to ensure quality execution of both building and strategy.

Therefore, it is thought that the complex intertwining of the analytical phase and the synthesis of the project could be represented not only by drawings but also with explanatory essays (about the decisions and the descriptions of the contents) which could constitute a document of fast consultation for the operative phases of the project, and which could also be used for future works of this kind. The considerable length of time taken by the survey (and by the administrative response to the decisions made) could in the long run compromise the direct control over the project. Therefore these descriptive essays could represent, more than drawings, the dialectic of the project; they would not imply specific solutions, as do drawings, but instead would assert a general strategy with which to proceed. Articulating the plurality of operations, it will be possible to indicate certain programs through a simple system of coordinates, which will correspond to: different materials to be restored (describing with precision the techniques); the integration of certain materials (supported by historical reasons); and the design of modern integrations (to repair the fractures produced by the various demolitions). The ancient and post-ancient structures will be restored within every building unit, emphasizing within the various recogniz-

able phases the less invasive interventions, with homogenous materials and construction techniques compatible with the ancient. Analogously, the level changes between modern and ancient layers will be bridged to re-establish the continuity of the ancient fabric.

The liberation of the Roman monument produced by these demolitions can suggest a program of restoration that will recompose the volumes of the city block using the minimum of space, while restoring also the front façade. New demolitions will not be proposed. However, it may be necessary to find a flexible method of intervention in order to recuperate even the partially damaged buildings. In this case, steel or concrete can be used as a visibly separate material for the connections or to welcome functions that are inadequate to the historical structures. The modern materials therefore won't be demonized, nor overly emphasized, but instead could be composed in the metamorphism of forms together with traditional and historical materials.

The city block exterior will be presented with the Renaissance profile (which was generated from the Roman monument); while using these instruments of historical sciences, it will be possible in the interior to re-create the idea of the large empty urban space generated by the demolitions of the 1940's. The large container of the Roman monument will go back to its ancient function of providing public space, at the center of the architectural complex of the block. It will be open towards the city through the paths of the medieval alleys and through the gardens and courtyards of the houses.

Many of these, although later incorporated into the palaces, are still visible as ancient limestone paths and wells that existed still in the time of the 1748 plan of Giovanbattista Nolli.

From the street level, the internal space can be articulated towards the excavations and the archaeological area, or towards the roofs that define the tops of the volumes which were left open from the demolitions of the 1940's; in this way, the interior can dynamically compose itself of ancient and modern, from continuously varying points of view.

CREDITS

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Fig. 1 – forma urbis romae
 Fig. 2 – campo marzio, g.b.nolli 1748
 Fig. 3 – via botteghe oscure, the restoration project of the balbo crypt
 Fig. 4,5,6 – the restoration project of the balbo crypt, main floor and sections
 Fig. 7-18 – ancient walls and new materials

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In this role, and detached at Pisa, she directed the restoration of some historical buildings in Livorno, Lucca and Volterra. When she was transferred to Rome, she directed the restoration works of the Colosseum, the Constantine Arch, the Caracalla Baths and lately of the Balbi crypt.

She published many studies about historical centers and urban restoration, about development of renaissance cities, and about the construction techniques of Roman cities. She coordinated the activities to develop and publish the guidelines for the restoration and recovery of historical center of Rome for the Ministry of Cultural affairs.

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